

QUALITY OF LIFE OF STUDENTS FROM URBAN AND RURAL ENVIRONMENTS OF GUANAMBI, BAHIA: COMPARATIVE STUDY

CALIDAD DE VIDA DE ESTUDIANTES DE ZONAS URBANAS Y RURALES DE GUANAMBI, BAHÍA: ESTUDIO COMPARATIVO

QUALIDADE DE VIDA DE ESTUDANTES DOS MEIOS URBANO E RURAL DE GUANAMBI, BAHIA: ESTUDO COMPARATIVO

Edivalda da Silva Domingues Lopes ¹

Lucas dos Santos ²

Claudio Bispo de Almeida ³

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Abstract

Quality of Life (QoL) is a multidimensional and subjective construct which carries a growing interest in various areas of human activity. The following work had as its objective to analyze the quality of life as perceived by urban and rural students from Guanambi, a municipality located in the state of Bahia, Brazil. This is an epidemiologic research with a cross-sectional approach involving students from two public schools from the Guanambi municipality. One of the schools in from the urban area, and the second, from the rural area. The chosen sample consisted of 167 volunteers. Our research used the WHOQOL-bref assessment to analyze the QoL, which evaluates four domains: Physical health, Psychological, Environment and Social relationships. The analysis were done via descriptive statistics, frequency distribution and, for the comparisons, the Mann-Whitney U test. Results show that the students from both rural and urban environments have close notions of the QoL, however, that QoL level is low (urban and rural areas: median = 50.00; $p = 0,988$)

Key-words: Quality of life; High school; Urban population; Rural population.

Resumen

La calidad de vida (CdV) es un constructo multidimensional y subjetivo cuyo estudio ha ido ganando creciente interés en diversas áreas de la actividad humana. Este estudio tuvo como objetivo analizar la CdV desde la perspectiva de estudiantes de áreas urbanas y rurales del municipio de Guanambi, Bahía, Brasil. Se trata de un estudio epidemiológico, con diseño transversal, realizado con estudiantes de dos escuelas del municipio de Guanambi, una ubicada en el área urbana y otra en el área rural. La muestra estuvo compuesta por 167 participantes. El instrumento utilizado para

¹ Master's in Teaching, Language and Society from the State University of Bahia. Teacher in the Bahia State Education Network.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8372-6568> Contato: edivalda.silva250@gmail.com

² Doctor of Health Sciences from the State University of Southwest Bahia. Professor at the State University of Tocantins. Member of the Epidemiology Research Group.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8195-8856> Contato: lsantos.ed.f@gmail.com

³ Doctor of Health Sciences from the State University of Southwest Bahia. Professor in the Postgraduate Program in Teaching, Language and Society at the State University of Bahia. Member of the Epidemiology Research Group.

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-9486-7163> Contato: cbalmeida@uneb.br

evaluar la CdV fue el cuestionario WHOQOL-bref, con ítems que evalúan cuatro dominios: físico, psicológico, ambiental y relaciones sociales. Los análisis se realizaron mediante estadística descriptiva y distribuciones de frecuencias, y se empleó la prueba U de Mann-Whitney para las comparaciones. Los resultados mostraron que los estudiantes de zonas urbanas y rurales tenían percepciones similares de la CdV, pero, en general, sus niveles de CdV eran bajos.

Palabras clave: Calidad de vida; Educación Secundaria; Población Urbana; Población Rural.

Resumo

A Qualidade de vida (QV) é um constructo multidimensional e subjetivo cujo estudo vem tendo interesse crescente em diversas áreas da atividade humana. Este estudo teve como objetivo analisar a qualidade de vida na percepção de estudantes dos meios urbano e rural do Município de Guanambi, Bahia, Brasil. Trata-se de uma pesquisa epidemiológica, com delineamento transversal realizada com estudantes de duas escolas do município de Guanambi, sendo uma localizada na área urbana e outra na área rural. A amostra constituiu-se de 167 participantes. O instrumento utilizado para avaliação da QV foi o questionário WHOQOL-bref, com itens que avaliam quatro domínios: Físico, Psicológico, Meio Ambiente e Relações Sociais. As análises foram feitas por meio de estatística descritiva, distribuição de frequências e, para as comparações, utilizou-se o teste U de Mann-Whitney. Os resultados mostraram que os estudantes dos meios urbano e rural apresentam percepções aproximadas de QV, porém, no geral, esse nível de QV foi baixo (zona urbana e zona rural: mediana = 50,00; $p = 0,988$).

Palavras-chave: Qualidade de vida; Ensino Médio; População urbana; População rural.

Introduction

Throughout history, the concept of Quality of Life (QoL) has been defined in many ways, in the search for understanding fundamental human needs. Considering the many cultures and living contexts, many instruments are being developed, being, at first, objective in nature, and considering measurable economical aspects such as the Human Development Index (HDI). With time, subjective aspects started being considered, such as well-being, personal accomplishment and life satisfaction (Sbizzarro Neto, 2016).

Cardoso Júnior, Cardoso and Nunes (2025) recognize QoL as a construct that consists of many concepts, including well-being and individual and communal values, with subjectivity being its main feature. As such, the perception of QoL can vary from one individual to the next or between the different contexts of which the individuals are a part of. Almost invariably, QoL is related to health, which for a long time was defined as the absence of disease. With the expansion of its conceptualization by the World Health Organization (WHO), other perceptions of QoL, too, have arisen, including in the educational sphere.

Through a literature review study, it has been observed that the QoL may be affected by factors like: socioeconomic aspects; gender; physical and mental health (Batista *et al.*, 2024). According to Souza and Marques (2010), university students are among the most studied groups, while high school students are hardly ever studied. In that context, Sousa, Lourenço and Amorim (2023) highlight the importance of scientific research projects aimed at students.

High school students are usually classified as teenagers, an age which "[...] presents its own biological characteristics, but the teenager must not be seen as a merely biological being, but also as a social being that is directly influenced by its environment, which interferes with their behavior" (Pereira *et al.*, 2021, p.2). This life period brings various biological, psychological and social transformations, all of which may cause conflict, crisis and contradictions (Oliveira *et al.*, 2025).

According to the 2019 research by the National School Health Research (Pesquisa Nacional de Saúde do Escolar – PeNSE) about the usage of healthcare services by Brazilian teenagers, “56.56% of teenage students have looked for healthcare service or for professionals for care related to their own health. The pursuit was less frequent in male students, Black, mixed, Asian and Indigenous students, public school students and students from rural areas” (Silva *et al.*, 2023, p.6)

There are many different causes for death among teenagers: “the different levels of risk of passing for teenagers in Brazil can also be explained by living and housing conditions in municipalities and in the states.” (Malta *et al.*, 2021, p.2) According to Santana *et al.*, (2021), teenagers living in rural areas, and ones from *quilombo* communities live with limited quality and have trouble accessing healthcare services, as well as facing difficulty to reach healthcare stations due to geographical isolation; living dynamics that create singular situations that must be taken into account when organizing a healthcare structure for this population.

On the other hand, intense urbanization worldwide has produced deep changes in people's daily life as well as their health (Pereira; Caiaffa; Oliveira, 2021). Most of the threats to teenagers' health come from behavioral factors. According to WHO (2013), insufficient physical exercising, substance abuse and eating disorders are risky behaviors when it comes to health, not only for its direct influence in the health-illness phenomenon, but also in regards to future behaviors (Vieira *et al.*, 2015).

Schools are a place for socialization; a place where different individuals with different ways of thinking and living are found, and where various subjects are learned, making it possible to acquire knowledge related to different modes of life. It becomes relevant to discuss QoL and the health of high school students given that teenagers are still in development, and may still be guided towards healthy eating habits, regular exercising, harmonious relationships with the environment, healthy interpersonal relationships and elements that promote positive health.

Since current literature is lacking further studies, researching the QoL of healthy high school students may contribute to sustaining and developing other studies, as well as providing a notion of the living conditions of this societal group, of the perception of students from different contexts such as rural and urban environments, and finally, to identifying groups with higher risk of health issues and compromised well-being. Teenagers who are vulnerable to a lower QoL can be found in school environments, which makes schools convenient places for healthcare education acts aiming for lifestyle changes, and for the consolidation of public policies for the betterment of the students' QoL.

It is within this context that this research's question arises: What is the perception of QoL of students from the urban and rural environments of Guanambi, Bahia, Brazil? To answer this question, this study intended to analyze the QoL in the rural and urban region student's perception, in the context of the municipality of Guanambi, Bahia, Brazil.

Method

This is an epidemiological research with a cross-sectional approach and convenience sampling of students from two schools, one located in the urban area and the other in the rural area of the Guanambi municipality in Bahia, Brazil, which is 796 kilometers away from Salvador, a city that represents strong influence in the commercial area. According to the data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística - IBGE, 2022), the population of Guanambi was of 87817 people and the total area was of 272,367 km².

In 2023, when the data was collected, the city of Guanambi had four (04) state funded public high schools, three of which are in the city, and one, in the rural area. Of the three city schools, one offers professional education, and another offers full-time education⁴. Only one of the schools offers part time schooling like the one from the rural area. The *locus* of the research were two state funded public schools, one in the city, one in the countryside. One accommodates the largest, and the other, the smallest number of high school students, however both schools offer high school in part time hours, though with distinct locations and methodologies.

The rural school is located in the district of Mutã, 32 kilometers away from the city of Guanambi. It offers Rural High Schooling and Adult High School (Educação de Jovens e Adultos - EJA) with a total of 200 students enrolled and divided into 8 classrooms in 2023. Meanwhile, the Urban High School in the city had 1,123 students enrolled. Therefore, together, the schools served 1,323 students, which was considered the population for this study.

The population consisted of teenagers and young adults enrolled into High School in the researched schools, who also volunteered as participants to this research. The sample size was calculated, taking into account the student quantity in each school, a confidence level of 95%, and margin of error of 5%, which results in a sample size of 283 participants. Classes were randomly chosen so that all three Brazilian High School years were included. All students were clearly told about what participating would entail, and would only be allowed to participate if they signed the Informed Consent Form as adults and legal guardians for minors, and the Informed Assent Form for minors who were present in the day of the data collection.

Intellectually disabled students and students who, when informed about the research project, did not agree to the terms or chose not to come to School for any of the data collection stages were considered unsuitable for participation. On data collection days, many students did not bring signed forms, making it impossible to include them, since they did not have the consent from their legal guardians, or they simply had no interest in participating. This was more frequent in the urban school.

⁴ Regular classes in Brazil are usually either strictly during mornings, afternoons, or at night. Full time schools include extracurricular activities on the opposite shift.

As such, the sample could not reach the necessary percentage, making it a non-representative sample. For that reason, a non-randomized convenience sample was chosen, composed by 167 students. In research projects, if a representative sample is impossible, "one must settle for the best possible sample, always aiming for it to be at least minimally representative. This kind of sample is called a convenience sample" (Zangirolami-Raimundo; Echemberg; Leone, 2018, p.3).

The study was submitted to the Research Ethics Committee of the State University of Bahia (Universidade do Estado da Bahia), following the Resolution nº 466 of the National Health Council (Conselho Nacional de Saúde), December 12th, 2012, because its research involves human beings. It received a favorable response under Statement nº5.937.398. The students gave their consent via Informed Consent Form. The minors had to give their consent as well as the Informed Consent Form signed by their legal guardians.

The collection of data took place in September, 2023. Researchers, professors and university students formed a team of 10 people total. Initially, the concerned institutions were contacted, and the research explanation and distribution of the Informed Consent Form was scheduled. The questionnaire application happened one school at a time.

For data collection, two questionnaires were used. One is a socio-demographic form composed of eight questions picked from the National Health Research (Pesquisa Nacional de Saúde) by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística - IBGE, 2019). The other is a civil instrument developed by WHO, called WHOQOL-bref. This second questionnaire is composed by 26 multiple choice questions, and takes into account the past 15 days in the life of the participants. The four domains composing the questionnaire (Physical health, Psychological, Environment and Social relationships) can be evaluated by 24 items. The WHOQOL-bref form also has two general questions which evaluate the QoL and health of the participants (Fleck *et al.*, 2000).

The domains that compose the WHOQOL-bref questionnaire are: Physical health; Psychological; Environment and Social relationships. The Physical Health domain includes pain and discomfort, energy and fatigue, sleep and rest, mobility, daily life activities, dependency on medication or treatment and work capacity. The Psychological domain includes positive feelings, thinking, learning, memory and focus, self-esteem, body image and appearance, negative feelings, spirituality, religion and personal beliefs. The

Environment domain consists of the home environment, financial resources, health and social care: availability and quality, opportunity to acquire new information and new abilities, participation in recreational and leisure opportunities, physical environment (pollution/noise/traffic/climate) and transport. The Social Relationships involve personal relationships, social support and sexual activity.

As for the QoL perception, the variable was dichotomized, with "very bad", "bad" and "neither bad nor good" being considered "Bad", and "good" and "very good" being considered "Good". The domain calculation followed Fleck's (2000) proposal.

The analysis were made using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (IBM-SPSS 21.0, 2013, Inc, Chicago, IL). The WHOQOL-bref questions were designed for answers in *Likert* type scales, which can be later re-categorized. Each domain's score was obtained in a scale from 0 to 100 and recorded in average terms, as defined by the manual produced by the WHOQOL team, where higher averages suggest better perception of QoL.

This research used descriptive statistics, absolute and relative frequency distributions for categorical variables and averages with standard of deviation for continuous variables, medians, interquartil ranges (IQR) and percentage values (P). For inferential statistics, bivariate analysis was used. Initially Pearson's chi-squared test (X^2) was chosen for checking the connection between socioeconomic characteristics, quality of life and the location of the analyzed schools. It should be highlighted that Fischer's exact test was used when frequencies lower than five ($n < 5$) were verified.

The pairwise comparison of the independent variables' frequencies between the schools' locations was verified via Bonferroni's Post Hoc test in order to minimize type I errors (Macdonald; Gardner, 2000). Finally, the normal distribution of the QoL scores was tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Since all of them had non normal distribution, the nonparametric statistical test known as the Mann-Whitney U test was chosen for the comparisons. For each of the analysis, the defined statistic significance was of 5% ($\alpha = 0,05$).

Results

167 students were part of this study, of which 59 were male, 105 were female, and 3 declared to be part of a different gender. All of them enrolled into High Schools, one of them in the city, and another in a District of the Guanambi Municipality, Bahia. Out of all participants, 75 study in a urban environment, and 92 study in a rural environment. The median of the students' ages in the urban environment was of 18,00 (IQR: 1,00). The median of the ages in the rural high school was of 17,00 (IQR: 2,00) ($p = 0,061$).

In Table 1 we can see that both schools have similar statistical proportions of female students (urban area: 41,90%; rural area: 58,10%; $p = 0,123$). It was also noticeable that, in the rural area, there is a bigger number of students in the first and second high school year (77,40%), while in the urban area there is a higher number of students in the third and final high school year (58,10%) ($p < 0,001$). Among the morning class students, 96,30% were in the urban area, while 61,10% of afternoon class students and 100% of night class students were in the rural area ($p < 0,001$) (Table 1).

It was also noticeable that in both schools most students were single - 41,90% in the urban area, 58,10% in the rural area ($p < 0,056$). 57,60% of the students who live with their families were from the rural school, and 100% of students who live on their own were from the urban school ($p = 0,011$). In regards to work, 69% of the students who worked 20 hours a week were from the urban area, and 31%, from the rural area ($p = 0,014$). Lastly, analysis of family income showed that 63,50% of students whose family income was equal or inferior to two Brazilian minimum wages were from the rural area, while 84,60% of students whose family income ranged from three to five minimum wages were from the urban area ($p < 0,001$).

Table 1 - Analysis of the connection between socio-economical characteristics and the QoL of High School students from the analyzed Schools. Guanambi-BA, Brazil, 2023.

Variables	Urban High School		Rural High School		X ²	Value of p
	n	%	n	%		
Gender					3,805	0,123*
Male	28	47,50	31	52,50		
Female	44	41,90	61	58,10		
Other	03	100,00	00	00,00		

School Year					19,873	<0,001
1st year	07	22,60 ^a	24	77,40 ^b		
2nd year	07	22,60 ^a	24	77,40 ^b		
3rd year	61	58,10	44	41,90		
Class hours					42,076	<0,001
Morning classes	26	96,30 ^a	01	3,70 ^b		
Afternoon classes	49	38,90 ^a	77	61,10 ^b		
Night classes	00	0,00 ^a	14	100,00 ^b		
Civil status					5,288	0,056*
Single	62	41,90	86	58,10		
Married/Stable Union ⁵	04	57,10	03	42,90		
Other	09	75,00	03	25,00		
Living					7,293	0,011*
Alone	04	100,00 ^a	00	0,00		
With family	67	42,40 ^a	91	57,60 ^b		
Other	04	80,00	01	20,00		
Work					8,564	0,014
Does not work	49	40,80	71	59,20		
Up to 20 weekly hours	20	69,00 ^a	09	31,00 ^b		
Over 20 weekly hours	06	33,00	12	66,70		
Family income					22,385	<0,001*
Up to 2 MW	50	36,50 ^a	87	63,50 ^b		
3 to 5 MW	22	84,60 ^a	04	15,40 ^b		
6 or more MW	03	75,00	01	25,00		
Quality of Life					0,037	0,848
Good	54	45,40	65	54,60		
Bad	21	43,80	27	46,20		

χ^2 : test statistic; n: absolute frequencies; %<: relative frequencies; MW: minimum wages; *value of p obtained via Fischer's exact test; ^a e ^b statistically different frequencies verified via Bonferroni correction. **Source:** Author's own production

Table 2 shows the analysis of the general QoL of the students and the domains that compose it. No statistical differences were found in the median scores of the different area students WHOQOL-bref ($p > 0,05$). However, in both locations the lowest scores were in the physical domain, and the highest, in the social relationships domain. Finally, both urban and rural school students showed similar quality of life levels, with medians around the order of 50 ($p = 0,988$).

⁵ Similar to Common Law Marriage. Legally binding in Brazil

Table 2 - Comparative analysis of quality of life, verified via WHOQOL-bref, between urban and rural High School students. Guanambi - BA, Brazil, 2023.

Variables	Urban High School (n = 75)	Rural High School (n = 92)	Value of p
General quality of life	50,00* (P25: 37,50; P75: 50,00)	50,00* (P25: 37,50; P75: 50,00)	0,988
Physical health domain	25,00* (P25: 17,85; P75: 32,14)	26,78* (P25: 21,42; P75: 35,71)	0,391
Psychological domain	29,16* (P25:25,00; P75:41,66)	33,33* (P725: 25,00; P75: 41,66)	0,193
Social Relationships domain	41,66* (P25: 25,00; P75: 50,00)	41,66* (P25:33,33; P75: 50,00)	0,683
Envinroment domain	34,37* (P25:21,85; P75: 43,75)	28,11* (P25: 21,87; P75: 37,50)	0,246
Domain sum	32,55* (P25: 24,77; P75: 38,54)	33,25* (P25: 24,54; P75: 38,35)	0,928

n: absolute frequency; P: percentage; * median. **Source:** Author's own production

Discussion

This study analyses students' perceptions of QoL in both urban and rural environments in the Guanambi Municipality, Bahia (BA), Brazil. The students' profile shows a majorly female public. The largest participation percentage came from the 1st and 2nd High School years in the rural area, and from the 3rd year in the urban area, a difference which is justified by the convenience sampling. Urban first and second year high school students barely showed any interest in participating in the research, which made contacting the 3rd high school year, where students showed to be curious about the study, more convenient. In the rural high school, there students from the primary high school years were more willing to participate.

In regards to living, most volunteer students who lived with their family studied at the rural high school, while the ones who lived alone studied at the urban high school. This demonstrates that rural area teenagers live in their family's home for a longer time. In a study made by Fernandes and Zan (2017) involving students from Guanambi's rural area it was revealed that these students maintain strong bonds with their family, especially when it comes to fighting together for financial stability. A significant number of them made it clear that their families directly interfere in their teenage experience, in their life projects, and in their world views.

On the other hand, city teenagers who live alone show that the families are going through the process of detaching themselves from the nuclear family model. Conceição (2023, p.26) signifies independence: “It is believed that the best way to understand independence is as something every one should have, but in the right amount: being able to do their own things, get their own money, live alone if they wish to [...]”.

As for working hours, there is a significant difference between participants. Urban students were shown to have permanent jobs with predefined working hours. Most rural students, on the other hand, declare not to have jobs. It is known that it is harder for rural teenagers and young adults to enter the job market, resulting in them working in the farms alongside their families from an early age.

According to a study by Farias and Lopes (2021) about young rural people and their struggle for education and for jobs in Brazil, there are many barriers between them and social inclusion. Among their demands are the need for public policies that guarantee access to education and to jobs, as well as support for family farms. “Education and labor are put as baselines for the development of social projects that both concern young rural people as protagonists in society, and that have democratization of the land, of knowledge and of opportunities as their goal” (Faria; Lopes, 2021, p.13).

The difference in labor in the country side and in the city are quite revealing in order to understand the rural flight. Teenagers and young adults from the Mutã District, much like many other young people from the Brazilian countryside, suffer with the lack of public policies focused on the rural environment, and have their staying in the countryside restricted due to material and sociocultural conditions resulting from historic constructions and the current influence of agribusiness in modes of production (Silva, 2015). Seasonal migration is a phenomenon which, according to Nogueira *et al.* (2014), is present in the District. The community's migration process is more of a structural issue than a individual choice, most often for sowing sugar canes in the state of São Paulo and for working on bakeries in the city of Curitiba, in the state of Paraná. As such, the education process in the District is marked by abandonment of classes and low study progression rates (Silva, 2015).

Although the living conditions between both groups are different, the general perception of QoL is similar, which might be explained by other aspects involved in the construct. Urban students have larger family income compared to rural students, but it can

be said that the cost of living in the city is higher: “Despite the economic growth from recent times, there is still a large disparity in the income and the well being, not to mention different costs of living in different regions of Brazil, especially in the city” (Galvão *et al.*, 2016, p.201). It is clear that both urban and rural students present low QoL, a fact that suggests that High Schools students are in need of more attention.

In the absence of comparative studies between urban and rural students' QoL, our results are close to the one from Campus' *et al.* (2020) study which focuses on elderly people from urban and rural environments, and shows that, despite the fact that the urban population had more resources than the rural population, the difference in QoL was not significant. Despite the better economic levels from the urban population, which gives easier access to leisure activities, technology and health care, life in the countryside offers more contact with natural environments, less pollution and larger possibilities of well being.

The rural students' higher median in the Psychology domain may be justified by their direct contact with the environment. In addition, it was revealed during research that rural students were part of a psychological service project developed by the School itself, as well as emotional health workshops organized by the Educa Mais Bahia program, developed by the Department of Education of the State of Bahia (Secretaria de Educação do Estado da Bahia). Neither of the projects are present in the urban school.

In both locations, the Physical Health domain was the most critical. This is the part of the QoL that involves an active lifestyle, healthy diet, energy, work capacity and need for medical treatment. A study by Almeida *et al.* (2020) concerning socio-demographic and behavioral aspects associated with positive perception of their own health among teenage High School students in the Guanambi municipality showed that 69% of the students positively classified their own health; however, the consumption of alcoholic beverages, which is considered hazardous to health, even if not statistically associated with the study, was shown to receive over 75% positive consumption responses. Among the variables were sex, age group, experience with drugs, physical exercise and self perception of stress, this last one being the only variable associated with one's own positive perception of their health.

The need for medical treatment to accomplish daily activities is part of the Physical Health domain of the QoL where the participants of this research appeared fragile, which might be related to the impact of the COVID 19 worldwide pandemic in the years of 2020 and 2021 and the difficult access to health care services, especially for the rural population. A study by Silva *et al.* (2023) informs that socially vulnerable situations are determining factors when it comes to rural teenagers looking for health care services, and that Black, indigenous, Asian, public school attendees and students from the rural area had sought health care services and professionals the least. In that same study, the authors highlight that schools stand as places for acts for the promotion health, for creating healthy environments and for consolidating public policies such as the Health in School Program (Programa Saúde na Escola - PSE), which was conceived as a strategy to promote health care, prevention of worsening cases, and better QoL for High School students (Silva *et al.*, 2023).

In both contexts, the Social Relationships domain, which incorporates personal relationships, social support and sexual activity, was the domain with the best results, which might be justified by the fact that the teenagers live in groups, be it in person or through technology that, nowadays, is present even in places further from the city. "The living environment of young people becomes important when we get ourselves to know them. We can see that the countryside and the city are not disconnected or closed off in borders" (Fernandes; Zan, 2017, p.120).

Subjective happiness, social support, socio-demographic aspects and family and school support are important variables that are being considered in the perception of a higher QoL, especially in the Social Relationships domain, as is shown by a few studies, as well as the promotion of personal and social competence as a strategy to promote the well being of teenagers (Bica *et al.*, 2020; Gaspar *et al.*, 2006; Leal; Flório; Zanin, 2020).

The participants also revealed that they are satisfied with their sexual life. It is known that there is a high incidence of teenage pregnancy and of Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs). Celeste and Cappelli (2020) emphasize the role of the schools in sexual education, given that that is a fitting environment for learning about prevention methods for both pregnancy and STIs, and for the development of student autonomy. The results of all WHOQOL-bref's domains were added and the averages were found. Both the rural

and the urban areas show similar results, however this indicates a low QoL in both researched schools, and that suggests a need for attention for the health and the QoL of High School students on both contexts.

It is necessary to highlight that this research has limitations. It should be stressed that the selection of the sample that serves as a base for the data was made by convenience, and that impedes the generalization of the results. Another factor which must be considered is the lack in literature related to studying the QoL of healthy teenagers in the rural environment. However, it is important to stress that this study can contribute to cover the existing holes in the study of QoL in healthy teenagers, even if it is comparative between urban and rural contexts. It also hears from High School students about their perceptions and subjectivity.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the QoL perception of urban and rural High Schools students in the Guanambi Municipality, Bahia, was similar, without significant differences in the general QoL, the four domains composing the WHOQOL-bref or the global QoL, which is the average between all domains. However, both schools present low levels of general QoL, which reveals the need for educational and health care acts both in family and school spheres, aimed at the lives of High School students, and reiterating the need for public policies in order to better the QoL of this population.

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